

Valorisation of neglected plant

Introduction

OG SambucusValor aimed to develop value-added food products from elderberries, with a view to increasing their market penetration. It was assumed that the management and valorisation of elderberry cultivation based on the creation of quality indicators and sustainable production and transformation strategies, namely through the integration of skills and resources installed in partner entities, which should lead to the creation of a pilot centre to enhance this development.

Objectives and results

1. Definition of flower and berry quality indicators, which relate growing conditions to flower and berry composition;
2. Implementation of flower and berry stabilization and storage processes with a view to preserving their bioactive components for a period longer than the normal harvesting of materials, thus ensuring the continuous supply of raw materials with strict food quality standards;
3. Design and development of new food products, based on elderberry flowers and berries;
4. Nutritional assessment of products to be developed;
5. Creation of a website, information dissemination networks and a partnership network with consumer associations, food companies and elderberry producers as a means of disseminating, communicating and valuing elderberry, at national and international level;
6. Creation of a pilot elderberry centre that should represent a nucleus of innovation across the entire elderberry value chain: from the plant to the creation of new value-added food products.

The results are made available through diverse technical (p.ex : Publicação Uaonline: Investigação do Departamento de Química: Centro-piloto do sabugueiro nasce para desenvolver produtos alimentares mais saudáveis – notícia no site da UA on-line - <http://uaonline.ua.pt/pub/detail.asp?lg=pt&c=54222>) and scientific publications. An impressive number of presentations and workshops and other events were organized. A PhD thesis was supported by the OG activities.

Lessons learned

Promotion of elderberry products in baskets: In January 2021, Inovterra, in partnership with some farmers and with the partner entities of the Operational Group, launched a distribution of baskets of vegetables and regional products at national level. This launch of product baskets made making it possible to include elderberry products in sales to the public in a different way and made it possible to publicize elderberry-based products, which were presented every week in the baskets. Also, beginning of cooperation with Galiza (Spain) due to common interests. Involvement between producers and commerce, for renewed products and presentations, as well as in marketing activities. Involvement of the agroindustry.

Figures 1 and 2. Elderberry plant, product made from Elderberry

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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<https://youtu.be/SdjiiO15zKs>; <https://youtu.be/ZZAOQxeEazs>; <https://youtu.be/17Ep-wlLw3o>

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